

Milestone: M1.2 Project KPIs presented to MB

Lead Participant: ELIXIR Hub

Author: Mado Fernandez (ELIXIR)

Due: 31 January 2025 (M12)

Date Of Completion: 06/03/2025

Means of Verification

- [Managing Board meeting agenda](#) (6th March 2025)
- [Project Monitoring spreadsheet](#) tab detailing KPI progress until M12 and plans to M24

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes, to gather all the relevant information from Work Package Leads.

Project participants & others

ELIXIR Hub, WP Leaders

Next action steps

Follow up report due in Jan 2026

ELIXIR-STEERS is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101131096.

